

IMPACT OF MOBILE FOLLOW UP PROTOCOL OF CARE ON PREGNANCY OUTCOMES AMONG PREECLAMPTIC WOMEN: A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL (RCT)

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Abstract

Background: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) which includes preeclampsia (PE) constitute one of the leading causes of maternal and perinatal mortality worldwide, the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in monitoring preeclampsia has revolutionized maternal healthcare by enabling early detection, personalized management, and improved outcomes. **The aim:** was to evaluate the impact of mobile follow-up protocol of care on the pregnancy outcomes among preeclamptic women. **Design:** A randomized controlled trial (RCTs) design was adopted for this study. **Sample:** Purposive sample of (100) women with mild preeclampsia, were randomly recruited and randomly assigned in two group, 50 women in the study group who received routine hospital care and mobile follow-up protocol of care utilizing motab3a mobile app, and 50 women in the control group who received routine hospital care only. **Tools:** three tools were used for data collection; 1) Structured interview schedule 2) Initial assessment and maternal /fetal follow up tool and 3) Maternal, fetal and neonatal outcomes evaluation tool and Motab3a mobile application and instructional booklets as a supportive materials. **Results:** the results of current study revealed that there is statistical significance differences between groups regarding systolic and diastolic blood pressure, weight gain and edema degree ($p=0.001$), the results showed that women who received follow-up and monitoring through Motab3a mobile app showed better pregnancy outcomes as compared to control group. As; decrease occurrence of severe preeclampsia, APH, hospital admission, preterm delivery, PPH. Low rate of fetal complications as; oligohydromious, IUGR as compared to the control group, and NICU admission, neonatal weight and gestational age among motab3a app group had lower rate as compared to the control group with ($p<0.05$). **Conclusion:** women with mild preeclampsia who utilize follow-up protocol of care through motab3a mobile application is associated with better pregnancy outcomes. **Recommendations:** integrate a new technology in monitoring women who at risk during pregnancy and follow up protocol of care should be included in health care system for all risky groups and to be a part from antenatal care.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Preeclampsia, Follow-Up, Pregnancy Outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) which includes preeclampsia (PE), gestational hypertension, and preeclampsia superimposed on chronic hypertension, are significant contributors to morbidity and mortality worldwide, globally it has been estimated that preeclampsia complicates 2% to 10% of pregnancies, hypertensive disorders are responsible for almost 26% of maternal deaths, whereas in Africa and Asia they contribute to 9% of deaths. Although maternal mortality is much lower in high-income countries than in developing countries, 16% of maternal deaths can be attributed to hypertensive disorders (Gemechu, Assesfa & Mengistie., 2020).

American College of Obstetrics and Gynecology (ACOG, 2020) define preeclampsia as following; it is a multisystem disorder unique to human pregnancy, characterized by new-onset hypertension along with the involvement of one or more other organ systems and/or the fetus. Although elevated blood pressure is often, but not always, the first sign, proteinuria is the most commonly recognized additional feature. However, proteinuria is no longer considered a mandatory criterion for diagnosing the condition. According to most international guidelines, preeclampsia can be diagnosed when hypertension develops after 20 weeks of pregnancy and is accompanied by any signs of organ involvement, including renal insufficiency, hematological abnormalities, or liver and neurological complications (Hoyert, 2020).

The National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) guidelines (2022) classify women as high risk for preeclampsia if they have a history of hypertensive disease in a previous pregnancy or if they have pre-existing conditions such as chronic kidney disease, autoimmune diseases, diabetes, or chronic hypertension. Women are considered at moderate risk if they are nulliparous, aged 40 or older, have a body mass index (BMI) of 35 kg/m² or higher, have a family history of preeclampsia, are carrying multiple fetuses, or have a pregnancy interval of more than 10 years.

A study conducted by Mousa et al., (2022) to identify the maternal and fetal outcomes of preeclampsia. They reported that, cesarean section (CS) rates were significantly higher in the preeclampsia group as compared to the control group. The most common reasons for CS included; the severity of preeclampsia, placental abruption, and eclampsia. Birth weight was significantly lower in the preeclampsia group, with 5.6% of cases attributed to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and 3.4% linked to intrauterine fetal death (IUFD). Additionally, the leading causes of neonatal mortality in the preeclampsia group were prematurity, congenital abnormalities, and respiratory distress syndrome.

Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing an increasingly important role in the detection, management, and prediction of preeclampsia. By utilizing machine learning algorithms and advanced data analytics, AI can process large amounts of patient data—such as electronic health records, laboratory results, and vital signs—to identify patterns and risk factors linked to preeclampsia (Zhang, Li, & Liu, 2020). Early detection is crucial for managing the condition, and AI-powered tools can improve screening accuracy by integrating various datasets to offer clinicians valuable insights (Bujold, Roberge, &

Nicolaides, 2024). Furthermore, AI-driven predictive models can assess the likelihood of preeclampsia recurrence in future pregnancies, allowing for personalized antenatal care plans (Xiong & Smith, 2024).

Significance of the Study

In Egypt, the prevalence of HDP is (4.2%) suffering from Pregnancy Induced Hypertension (PIH), (3.8 %) had PE and eclampsia was (0.3%) (Gabal, Abousaif, Salah-Eldin and Abdelaziz, 2016). In addition, According to WHO (2016), maternal mortality ratio is 45 per 100000 live births.

From clinical experience, it was observed that preeclampsia can progress rapidly and cause serious maternal, fetal and neonatal complications. If these complications are not detected or treated as early as possible, they will lead to maternal and fetal mortality and morbidity. Several women with mild preeclampsia who treated at home were not monitored by herself or even by health care provider during home stay, they monitored only during visit to outpatient clinic, during this period they may develop serious complications from course of disease. At the same time they are unaware to these complications, how to deal and where to go. Through conducting the current study pre-eclamptic women will receive regular follow up and health instructions about disease danger signs of preeclampsia, their diet, rest and activities, environment, medications and all cases will be monitored and directed in case of emergency.

To date, there is scanty of quality evidence in the literature to guide clinical practice on utilizing technology for monitor progression of preeclampsia. This study will increase the knowledge-base about the benefits of new modality regarding monitoring progression of preeclampsia and pregnancy outcomes through mobile applications. As well as the findings of the current study may improve the quality of care and help in decrease maternal mortality and morbidity. In addition, findings of the current study may encourage policy maker in clinical setting to integrate mobile application in obstetrics, that might help in regular follow up and monitoring so complications can be detected and treated early as well as prevention of bad progression.

Theoretical Framework

The current study is based on concepts from systems theory, as well as concepts derived from advantages of continuous follow up and monitoring of women with mild pre-eclampsia for blood pressure, protein urea, labs investigation, fetal movement and warning signs as well as preeclampsia protocol of care through motab3a mobile app.

The system theory developed by Ludwig Von Bertalanffy (1968) as explained by Newby (1996) and is called open system model. Existing theories had tended to be reductionist, understanding the whole by breaking it into its parts. Von Bertalanffy's introduction of systems theory changed that framework by looking at the system as a whole, with its relationships and interactions with other systems, as a mechanism of growth and change. This changed the way people looked at systems and led to a new language, popularizing terms such as open and closed systems, entropy, boundary, homeostasis, inputs,

outputs, and feedback (Maurer, 2021). The system consists of a set of interacting components, with a boundary that filters both the kind and rate of flow of inputs and outputs from the system. The general system theory is concerned with changes due to interaction between the various factors (variables) in a situation, Ludwig system theory model is based on four areas, input, throughput, output and feedback (Vandali, & Vijayaraddi. 2015).

Figure 1: Illustrate a system theory and mobile follow up protocol of care for women with mild preeclampsia

Aim of the Study

The aim of the current study is to evaluate the impact of mobile follow up protocol of care on the pregnancy outcomes among preeclamptic women.

Outcome Measures

Maternal outcomes

- Primary outcomes: admission either to hospital or Intensive Care Unit (ICU), antepartum hemorrhage (Abruptio placenta), sever preeclampsia, HELLP syndrome and eclampsia.
- Secondary outcomes: preterm delivery, emergency cesarean section and postpartum hemorrhage.

Fetal and neonatal outcomes:-

- Primary outcomes: Intra-uterine Growth Restriction (IUGR), intra- uterine fetal death (IUFD), diminished fetal movement and oligohydrominous.
- Secondary outcomes: preterm birth before 37 weeks of gestation, small for gestational age (SGA) , NICU admission, neonatal death and stillbirth.

Research Hypotheses

This study tested the following hypotheses in the RCT:

H: Women with preeclampsia who received mobile follow up protocol of care had better pregnancy outcomes than those who received the routine hospital care.

Sub-hypothesis 1: Preeclamptic women who received mobile follow up protocol of care were had lower rates of hospital and ICU admission, emergency Cs, antepartum hemorrhage, HELLP syndrome and eclamptic fits than those who received the routine hospital care.

Sub-hypothesis 2: Preeclamptic women who received mobile follow up protocol of care were had lower rates of IUGR, IUFD, and preterm delivery than those who received the routine hospital care.

Sub-hypothesis 3: Preeclamptic women who received mobile follow up protocol of care were had lower rates of SGA, neonatal death and stillbirth than those who received the routine hospital care.

Research Design

A randomized controlled trial (RCTs) was utilized to fulfill the aim of the proposed study. The sample was divided into two groups, a study and control group (n=50 for each group). The study group received routine hospital care and mobile follow up protocol of care by Motab3a APP, while the control group received the routine care of the hospital. Both groups were followed up prospectively till the first 24 hours after delivery.

Randomization;

Women who were meet the eligible criteria were recruited by a simple random sample using computer-generated random numbers, through randomizer software (<http://www.randomizer.org>). Random assignment of the subjects into two groups done through an opaque sealed envelope reflecting the type of each group, and then the eligible women asked to choose an envelope to determine their groups (control or study group).

Sample

A purposive sample of (100) women with mild preeclampsia who attended the antenatal outpatient high risk clinic, at EL Galaa teaching hospital, were recruited from the beginning of December 2023 till the end of(December /2024). According to the following inclusions criteria were pregnant women who was diagnosed as mild preeclampsia, can

read and write, have smart phone. While women with preeclampsia who had history of eclamptic fits, HELLP syndrome and experienced major complications of preeclampsia were excluded from the study.

Sample size: The sample size was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\hat{n} = \frac{n}{1 + \frac{z^2 \times \hat{p}(1-\hat{p})}{\varepsilon^2 N}}$$

Sample size = (80)

The estimated sample size was (80) women with mild preeclampsia calculated by using above formula, 20 % of the estimated number of women added to compensate the participants that dropout during data collection phase therefore, the total sample size will be (100) women with mild preeclampsia.

Consort chart:

Setting

The current study was conducted at the antenatal high risk clinic at El Galaa teaching hospital for obstetrics and gynecology. It is a university affiliated hospital that provides free Obstetrics and Gynecology health services.

Tools for Data Collection

Tool I) Structured Interview schedule: This tool was designed by the research investigator, and constituted of four parts; first part data related to demographic characteristics such as age, level of education, residence and occupation. Previous obstetric history which included data about parity, gravidity, history of abortion, preterm labor, maternal complications during previous pregnancy or mode of previous delivery presented in part two. The third part showed data related to this current pregnancy as LMP, EDD, GA. Data related to medical history (hypertension, cardiac, renal and autoimmune diseases), BMI and assessment of lifestyle pattern which included baseline data about dietary habits, sleeping pattern and exposure to smoking were presented in part four

Tool II) Initial and follow-up Maternal /fetal assessment tool:

This tool was designed by the researcher after extensive literature review and encompassed items regarding to initial antenatal and follow up assessment of the current pregnancy. It includes two parts: The first part was related to maternal assessment. It includes anthropometric measures such as weight, height and body mass index (BMI); degree of edema, proteinuria and lab investigation as liver enzyme (ALT, AST, ALP), Kidney functions (urea, creatinine, Albumin/ creatinine ratio) Complete blood count (hemoglobin, hematocrit and platelets count). The second part was related to fetal assessment through ultrasonography (U/S) which entailed; gestational age (GA), fetal heart rate (FHR), estimated fetal weight (EFW) and amniotic fluid index (AFI). As well as, fetal movement count (FMC) that was counted by the participants.

Tool III) Maternal, fetal and neonatal outcomes evaluation tool: this tool consists of three parts. **Part A**, included data related to maternal outcomes during pregnancy, labor and postpartum such as, admission to hospital or ICU; sever preeclampsia, eclamptic fits, HELLP syndrome in the form of (sever head ache, blurred vision, generalized edema, nausea and vomiting, epigastric pain, hemolysis of RBCs, elevated liver enzyme low platelet count), abruption placenta, emergency Cs, preterm delivery and postpartum hemorrhage. **Part B**, included data related to fetal outcomes as; IUGR, IUFD, oligohydrominous, decreased fetal movement also included (ultrasound and fetal Doppler report), **and Part C:** included data related to neonatal assessment as; prematurity, admission to NICU, neonatal death and stillbirth.

Supportive material. Entailed two materials; Motab3a mobile application and Instructions Booklet.

Motab3a mobile application: designed and all data available on mobile app prepared by research investigator as well as developed by AI expert, Motab3a mobile app entails

two parts, first part entailed an monitoring women with preeclampsia for (BP, weight, proteinuria, edema degree, fetal movement and labs investigation and second part entailed an health instructions about diet, rest and activities, environment, medications , exposure to smoking, which makes Motab3a mobile app has many prospective for caring women with preeclampsia (monitoring and educating).

Instructions Booklet: was prepared by research investigator, after extensive reviewing of literature, designed in simple Arabic language, instructions booklet divided in two parts, **part one** explained to the participants in details and pictures how they receive, down load motab3a app and steps how they input their data to app. **Part two** include all health instructions related to follow up of mild preeclampsia, appropriate diet, quiet and low-lighted environment, rest and activity, exposure to smoking, avoid over stress, compliance to medications. Follow up protocol of care which is available in instructions booklet based on (National Institute of Health and Care Excellence [NICE], (2022).

Procedure

The study conducted through the following steps; recruitment and randomization of sample, the interviewing, initial assessment, implementation; follow up and evaluation.

A. Recruitment and randomization of sample: Women who meet the eligibility criteria were recruited by a random sample, computer-generated random numbers using research randomizer software (<http://www.randomizer.org>). The study sample were randomly allocated into two groups (control or study group). Using an opaque sealed envelope reflecting the type of each group, and then the eligible women asked to choose an envelope to determine their groups

B. The interviewing: Face to face individualized interview, each participant in the study and control group who met the inclusion criteria was interviewed to collect base line data related to demographic characteristics, medical history, past and present obstetric history such as; gravida, parity, number of abortions, living children, still birth, preterm baby, mode of previous delivery and previous pregnancies complications. Assessment of the current pregnancy included items about the first day of last menstrual period (LMP) to calculate the expected date of delivery (EDD) and gestational age (GA), complications during this current pregnancy, and the current lifestyle pattern related to her diet, sleeping hour's exposure to smoking. The interview was face to face and took around 15 minutes for each participant individually on both groups.

C. Initial assessment during pregnancy. Initial assessment was performed for each participant in both groups on initial visit which was carried out at the recruitment time to obtain the baseline data such as;(maternal Blood pressure, proteinuria, degree of edema, weight, and BMI) and labs investigation, Fetal assessment (GA, weight and AFI) through US

D. Implementation. For the study group mobile follow up protocol of care for mild preeclamptic women was given to the participants in the study group, using Motab3a app and written instructional booklet (Appendix D) that was prepared by the research

investigator containing the same information to be reference for the participants (booklet was in Arabic using clear and simple language and colored photos) and Motab3a app.

D.1. During initial antenatal visit. The research investigator gave the participants in the study group an oral overview about preeclampsia (definition, risk factor, signs, symptoms and complications). Then, gave education session about how to monitor (blood pressure, weight, degree of edema, proteinuria, how to count fetal movement (FMC), warning signs of preeclampsia, then research investigator demonstrate and help the participants in the study group to down load Motab3a app, how to use it and input their data about BP, proteinuria, weight, fetal movement, labs investigation to Motab3a app, participants in study group informed about importance of input their data accurately because they will be monitored through app, and any abnormal data detected by Motab3a app this help in early detection, referral and management of the problem.

Participants in study group were received health educations about how to modify their habits regarding diet should be (low salt, low fats, avoid fast foods, take diet rich in fibers, green vegetables, protein, vitamin D, calcium, minerals and increase oral fluids intake up to 4 liters per day), as well as health teaching about environmental control to be quiet with appropriate light well ventilated environment, stress management, comply to course of treatment that was prescribed by physician, rest and activity were given to participants in the study group.

Furthermore the participants in the study and control group were informed that if they experienced warning signs of preeclampsia (severe headache with blurred vision, epigastric pain and vomiting, sudden weight gain) should be directed to nearest health care center to save their life and their fetus.

Feedback. The participants in study group were asked some questions to test their understanding the important information and allowing time if they want to ask question for more clarification and allow them to show how to use Motab3a app. All missed points repeated and clarified by research investigator.

E: Follow up and evaluation. Both groups (control and study group) advised to follow the routine schedule of antenatal care visits used in the outpatient antenatal high risk clinic regarding women preeclampsia, in Al-Galaa teaching hospital, antenatal high risk clinic schedule is case-dependent schedule depend on case condition, stability, prognosis and compliance. As well as each participant in the study and control group was assessed in each visit for anthropometric measurement, BP, Proteinuria, degree of edema, and lab investigation, as well as fetus assessment through the result of U/S and fetal Doppler to detect fetal complications.

All participants in study and control group were assessed for warning signs of preeclampsia that may occurred during pregnancy, and they advised to come immediately to the outpatient clinic or emergency unit if they experienced any of these signs regardless of the scheduled time of their visit.

Intrapartum assessment of the outcomes. The research investigator assessed participants in both groups for mode of delivery and complications related to the preeclampsia for participants and their neonates during intrapartum. This section took about 15 minutes for each group. The maternal complications were; emergency Cs, preterm labor.

Postpartum assessment of the outcomes. The researcher investigator assessed all participants' hospital records in both groups and their neonates during the first 24 hours postpartum in both groups. It included the following items the occurrences of maternal and newborn complications as; postpartum hemorrhage, neonatal respiratory distress syndrome, (SGA), NICU and neonatal death,

Statistical Analysis

Data were statistically described in terms of mean \pm standard deviation (\pm SD), or frequencies (number of cases) and percentages when appropriate. Because the groups are

Large enough, comparison of numerical variables between the study groups was done using Student t test for independent samples. For comparing categorical data, Chi-square (χ^2) test was performed. Exact test was used instead when the expected frequency is less than 5. Two-sided p values less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Table 1: Comparison of Demographic characteristics Data among Women in the Study and Control Group (N=100)

Items	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		χ^2	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Age (Years)						
≤ 20	12	24	11	22	2.11	0.71
-25	15	30	10	20		
-30	9	18	12	24		
-35	7	14	8	16		
≥ 35	7	14	9	18		
Mean \pm SD Yrs.	26.28 \pm 6.471		27.64 \pm 6.050		1.086	0.70
Educational level						
Primary educated	0	0	1	2	6.88	0.07
Preparatory educated	1	2	3	6		
Secondary educated	38	76	43	86		
University education	11	22	3	6		

Table (1) illustrates that, 24 % of women in the study group as compared to 22% in the control group their age < 20 years old with the mean age was 26.28 \pm 6.471 years old in the study group, as compared to 27.64 \pm 9 6.050 years old in the control group. About, 76% of woman in the study group as compared to 86 % in control group completed their secondary school education with no statistical significant differences among both groups.

Figure 2: showed that, 66 % of the study group as compared to 70% % in the control group were housewife. With no statistically significant differences between both groups ($X^2=0.18$, $p = 0.66$)

Figure 3: Comparison of women in the study group and control group in relation to their residence

Figure (3) illustrated that, 54% of women in the study group as compared to 64 % in the control group were lived in rural areas. With no statistically significant differences between both groups ($X^2=1.03$, $p = 0.31$).

Table 2: Comparison between the study sample in Relation to Their Previous Obstetric history (N=100)

Items	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		X ²	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Gravity						
Primigravida	27	54	19	38	5.33	0.37
Multigravida	23	46	27	54		
Grand multigravida	0	0.0	4	8		
Parity						
Nullipara	31	62	26	52	4.56	0.33
Primipara	5	10	6	12		
Multipara	14	28	18	36		
Gestational age at time of recruitment						
25-29	20	40	15	30	0.327	0.361
30-35	30	60	32	64		
Mean ± SD (weeks)	30.53 ± 2.408		30.03 ± 2.382		T test=1.044	0.29
Body mass index (BMI) category						
Normal weight	10	20	8	16	5.01	0.08
Overweight	27	54	30	60		
Obese	13	26	12	24		
Mean body mass index (BMI) mean						
BMI Mean ± SD	27.30 ± 2.819		27.74 ± 2.946		T test=0.756	0.45

Body mass index (BMI).

Table (2) showed that, 54% of women in the study group as compared to 38% of them in control group were primigravida. 62% of women in the study group as compared to 52% in the control group were nulliparous. Mean gestational age at time of recruitment in the study group was 30.53 ± 2.408 weeks as compared to 30.03 ± 2.382 weeks in the control group. About, 54% of women in the study group were overweight as compared to 60% of the control group, meanwhile 26 % of women in the study group were obese as compared to 24 % in the control group. With no statistical significant differences between both groups.

Table 3: Distributions of the study sample related to Their Ultrasound Results Especially Fetus Amniotic Fluid Index and fetal weight during the Initial and 2nd Antenatal Visit (N=100)

U/S result During antenatal visits	Initial visit				X ²	P Value	2 nd visit				X ²	P Value
	Study group n=50		Control group n=50				Study group n=50		Control group n=50			
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Amniotic fluid index (AFI)												
Average	48	96	46	92	2.04	0.36	50	100	42	84	1.09	0.29
Oligohydromnios	2	4	3	6			0	0.0	8	16		
Polyhydromnios	0	0.0	1	2			0	0.0	0	0.0		
Mean Fetal weight (M ± SD)	1449.80 ± 367.07		1549.36 ± 480.45				2059.40 ± 478.64		2049.80 ± 444.70			
	T test =1.16 P value =0.24						T test =0.10 P value =0.92					

*Statistical significant at P value <0.05. * U/S (Ultrasound).

Table 4: Distributions of the study sample Related to Their Ultrasound Results Especially Fetus Amniotic Fluid Index and fetal weight during the 3rd And 4th Antenatal Visit (N=100)

U/S result During antenatal visits	3 rd visit				X ²	P Value	4 th visit				X ²	P Value
	Study group (n=48)		Control group (n=47)				Study group (n=48)		Control group (n=37)			
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%			Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Amniotic fluid index (AFI)												
Average	47	97.9	45	95.7	2.04	0.36	46	95.8	29	78.4	8.6	0.003*
Oligohydramnios	1	2.1	2	4.3			2	4.2	8	21.6		
Polyhydramnios	0	0.0	0	0.0			0	0.0	0	0.0		
Mean Fetal weight (M ± SD)	2536.00 ± 376.15		2394.40 ± 326.94				2664.40 ± 263.80		2310.00 ± 245.15			
	T test=2.01 P value=0.04						T test= 6.95 P value = 0.001					

* Statistically significant at P value <0.05.

In relation to the result of ultrasound which carried out during antenatal visits to monitor fetal amniotic fluid index (AFI) and fetal weight, 96% in women of the study group as compared to 92 % in the control group were had normal AFI during the initial antenatal visit. Chi square test revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between both groups (X²=2.04, P value= 0.36) , during second antenatal visit 100 % in women of the study group as compared to 84 % in the control group have normal AFI.

During the third antenatal visit, 97.9 % in women of the study group as compared to 95.7% in the control group had average AFI, While, 2.1% & 4.3 % of women in the study and control group respectively have oligohydramnios. Chi square test revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between both groups (X²=2.04, P value= 0.36). While during fourth antenatal visit oligohydramnios presented in 4.2% in the study group as compared to 21.6 % in the control group.

Table 5: Distribution of The Study Sample in both Groups regarding Current Pregnancy complications among (N=100)

Items	Study group (n=7)		Control group (n=18)		X ²	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Sever preeclampsia	5	71.4	10	55.6	5.51	0.01*
HELLP syndrome	0	0.0	2	11		
Eclampsia	0	0.0	1	5.6		
Abruption placenta (APH)	2	28.6	5	27.8		

Numbers are not mutually exclusive, *Statistical significant at p value < 0.05, * PE (preeclampsia) *APH (antepartum hemorrhage).

Table (5) showed that, out of 7 (14 %) cases in the study group as compared to 18 (36%) of them in control group experienced maternal complications during pregnancy. 71.4 % of women in the study group versus 55.6 % in the control group complicated with sever preeclampsia, 28.6% versus 27.8 % of women the study and control group respectively experienced abruptio placenta.

Table 6: Distribution of the Study Sample in relation of admission to hospital and action taken during pregnancy (N=100)

Hospital admission	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		X ²	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Yes	11	22	19	38	3.04	0.08
No	39	78	31	62		
Action taken after admission	(n=11)		(n=19)		5.05	0.02*
Emergency Cs	2	18.2	16	84.2		
Observation & Follow-up	9	81.8	3	15.8		

Table (6) showed that, 22% of women in the study group as compared to 38% of women in the control group were admitted to hospital. 18.2 % of women in the study group as compared to 84.2 % in the control group were admitted for emergency Cs delivery, while 81.8 % of women in the study group as compared to 15.8 % in the control group admitted to hospital for observation and follow-up.

Figure 4: showed that, 4% of women in the study group as compared to 26 % in the control group delivered preterm. Chi square test revealed there is statistically significance differences between both groups (X²=7.16, p-value= 0.007)

Table 7: Distribution of the Study sample Related to Mode of delivery (N=100)

Items	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		X ²	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
NVD	4	8	1	2	1.89	0.16
Cs	46	92	49	98		
Type of Cs	(n=46)		(n=49)		8.19	0.004**
Planned Cs	42	91.3	33	67.3		
Emergency Cs	4	8.7	16	32.7		

*Highly Statistical significant at p value <0.001, Normal vaginal delivery NVD, Cesarean section Cs

Table (7) showed, 92% of women in the study as compared to 98% in the control group were delivered by caesarean section. About, 91.3 of women in the study group versus 67.3% in the control group delivered with planned Cs. While, 8.7% in the study group as compared to 32.7% in the control group had emergency Cs.

Figure 5: Gestational age at time of delivery by category among the study sample

Figure (5) showed that, 96 % of neonate among the study group versus 74% in the control group, were delivered at term gestational age 37 ≥ wks, while 4% of neonates in the study group versus 14 % in the control were delivered moderate to late preterm.

Table 8: Comparison between Women in both Groups Regarding to mean gestational age and neonatal weight at time of delivery (N=100)

Items	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		t- test	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Mean GA at time of delivery (M±SD)	37.30 ± 0.81		35.50 ±1.43		3.43	0.001**
Mean neonatal weight (gm)	2933.60 ± 293.77		2334.20 ±342.10		6.26	0.001**

*GA: Gestational Age, categories of GA according to WHO (2023). *Highly Statistically significant at p value <0.001

Table (8) showed that, mean gestational age at time of delivery was 37.30 ± 0.81 weeks in the study group as compared to 35.50 ±1.43 in the control group. T test revealed there is highly statically significance differences between both groups (t-test =3.43, p-value 0.001). At the same time mean neonatal weight at time of delivery was 2933.60 ± 293.77 gm in the study group as compared to 2334.20 ±342.10gm of newborn in the control group. T-test revealed there is highly statically significance differences between both groups (T test =6.26, p value 0.001).

Table 9: Distribution of the Study and Control Group Related to Maternal and neonatal postpartum Complications (N=100)

Maternal complications	Study group (n=50)		Control group (n=50)		χ^2	p-value
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%		
Yes	6	12	16	32	4.00	0.004**
No	44	88	36	72		
If yes mention						
Maternal PPH	1	2	4	8	3.45	0.06
Neonatal complications						
NICU admission	5	10	10	20	1.4	0.23
Still birth	0	0.0	2	4		
NICU stay/hour M±SD	36.6±73.5 1.5 day		163.7±123.6 7 days		T=2.09	0.005**

* Highly statistical significant at p value <0.05 * postpartum hemorrhage (PPH). Neonatal intensive care unit (NICU).

Table (8) showed that, 12% of women in the study group as compared to 32% in the control group was experienced postpartum complications. Chi square test revealed that, there is statistically significance differences between both groups ($\chi^2 =4.00$, p -value=.004). 2% versus 8 % in the study group and control group respectively experienced PPH. Meanwhile, neonatal complications as showed in table (19), 10 % of neonates in the study group versus 20 % in the control group were admitted to NICU. Chi square test revealed there is no statistically significance differences between both groups ($\chi^2=1.4$ p -value=0.23) and mean hours stay in NICU 36.6±73.5 hours of neonates in the study group as compared to 163.7±123 hours in the control group. Student T test revealed that there is statistical significance differences between both groups (t test =2.09, p -value=0. 005).

Table 10: Relative Risk of the study Sample in Relation to Maternal Complications occurred during Pregnancy

Items	RR in both groups N=100	95%CI RR		P value
		Lower	upper	
Sever Preeclampsia	0.500	0.184	1.358	0.01
HELLP syndrome	0.20	0.009	4.06	0.29
Eclampsia	0.09	0.005	1.60	0.10
APH	0.714	0.08	1.96	0.25

Table (10) showed that, the relative risk among women complications occurred during pregnancy were as the following; severe preeclampsia (RR 0.500, 95% CI 0.184, 1.358), HELLP syndrome (RR 0.20, 95% CI 0.009- 4.06), Eclampsia (RR 0.09, 95% CI 0.005- 1.60), antepartum bleeding (RR 0.714, 95% CI 0.237-2.150), The above mentioned relative risks were in favor of the study group that is to mean that follow protocol of care utilizing Motab3a app in the study group had a positive effect on the pregnancy outcomes in relation to (sever preeclampsia . HELLP syndrome, eclampsia and APH).

Table 11: Relative Risk of the study Sample in Relation to maternal Complications occurred during Delivery

Items	RR in both groups N=100	95% CI RR		P-value
		Lower	Upper	
Preterm labor	0.15	0.03	0.64	0.01
Intra-partum hemorrhage	0.28	0.03	3.09	0.33
Emergency CS	0.22	0.05	0.97	0.04

In relation to the relative risk of complications during labor among women in the study and control group; table (11) showed that; RR of preterm labor was= RR 0.15 (95% CI 0.03 -0.64), which mean that RR was in favor for the study group who applied follow up protocol of care using Motab3a app leading to decrease the risk of preterm labor that faced during the intrapartum rather than in the control group. Moreover, the relative risk of intrapartum Hemorrhage was= RR 0.28, (95% CI 0.03-2.09), which mean that RR was in favor for the study group who applied follow up protocol of care using Motab3a app leading to decrease the risk of intrapartum bleeding happened during delivery than in the control group. As well as, the relative risk of emergency Cs was= RR 0.22, (95% CI 0.05-0.97), that mean RR was in favor for the study group who applied follow up protocol of care using Motab3a app leading to decrease the risk of emergency Cs than in the control group.

Table 12: Relative Risk of the study Sample in Relation to Fetal Complications occurred during Pregnancy

Items	RR in both groups N=100	95% CI RR		P-value
		Lower	Upper	
Oligohydrominous	0.25	0.05	1.11	0.06
Decreased fetal movement	1.00	0.14	6.82	0.64
Absent fetal movement	0.50	0.04	5.33	0.56
IUGR	0.20	0.009	4.06	0.29
IUFD	0.33	0.01	7.99	0.49

In relation to the relative risk among fetal complications during pregnancy, table (12) illustrated that; relative risk was (RR= 0.25 95% CI 0.05 - 1.11) for Oligohydrominous, (RR= 0.5 95% CI 0.04- 5.33) for absent fetal movement, (RR= 0.20 95% CI 0.009- 4.06) for IUGR and (RR= 0.33 95% CI 0.01- 7.99) for IUFD, that mean RR was in favor for the study group who applied follow up protocol of care using Motab3a app decreased the risk of Oligohydrominous, absent fetal movement IUGR and IUFD than in the control group during pregnancy. While There was no difference between both groups in related to decreased fetal movement (RR= 1.00 95% CI 0.14 – 6.82) for decrease FMC.

Table 13: Relative Risk of the study Sample in Relation to Maternal and neonatal Complications during postpartum

Items	RR in both groups N=100	95% CI RR		P-value
		Lower	Upper	
PPH	0.25	0.028	2.159	0.20
NICU admission	0.50	0.18	1.35	0.17
Still birth	0.20	0.009	4.06	0.29

Table (13) illustrated that; relative risk for maternal complications during postpartum RR for PPH (RR 0.25, 95% CI 0.0289-2.1591). While the newborn complications during the postpartum period RR for NICU admission (RR 0.50, 95% CI 0.18-1.35), still birth (RR 0.20, 95% CI 0.009-4.06), That is to mean that RR was in favor for the study group, that mean applied of mobile follow up protocol of care using Motab3a app decrease the risk of maternal and neonatal complications during the postpartum regarding PPH, NICU admission and still birth among the study group as compared to the control group.

DISCUSSION

The current study was discussed within the frame of reference theoretical framework of a system theory approach which entails; input, throughput (process) and output. In addition answering research hypothesis; women with preeclampsia who received mobile follow up protocol of care were had better pregnancy outcomes than those who received the routine hospital care.

Section I: entails first approach of system theory (input)

The current study's findings revealed that, quarter of the study sample their age < 20 years old and mean age of the study and control group (26.28 ± 6.471 , 27.64 ± 6.050) respectively, more than three quarter of the study sample are secondary educated, more than two third of the study sample are housewife, and more than half of the study sample lives in urban area, more than half of the sample were primigravida, two third are nullipara, more than half of the study sample are overweight and quarter are obese, approximately quarter of the study group had previous pregnancy complications and nearly half of the study group had history of medical disease. Regarding the study group habits the result revealed that more than two third of the study group are exposed to passive smoking and 80 % of women don't exercise even walking.

So the current study's findings revealed that the risk factors for preeclampsia were primigravida, nulliparity, age, overweight and obesity, previous medical history e.g (autoimmune, chronic hypertension and diabetes), previous pregnancy complications e.g. Previous GHTN, Previous preeclampsia and GDM, exposure for smoking and sedentary life style.

In this regard, Egyptian studies were in consistence with the current study. The cross-sectional study conducted in Qena university hospital to identify prevalence and risk factors for preeclampsia among 300 pregnant women after 20 weeks of gestation. The results of the study revealed that the significant risk factors predisposing to preeclampsia were obesity, improper antenatal care, autoimmune disease, gestational diabetes mellitus, and advanced maternal age. By logistic regression analysis, high BMI was the most contributing risk factor associated with preeclampsia (p - value <0.0001) (Ameen et al., 2023).

Similarly, a cross sectional-cohort descriptive study was in consistent with the current study conducted by Ahmed, Hassanen, Abbas, & Kalaf (2018) to predict risk factors of preeclampsia among pregnant women attended antenatal clinic at Assiut university

hospital. They reported that, More than two fifths of the pregnant women's age from 18-25 years old. There was a significant relation between (body mass index and previous history of hypertension, diabetes and preeclampsia) and development of preeclampsia (p -value=0.000).

Section II; entails throughput (process) approach of system theory, through utilizing (Motab3a mobile app an instructional booklet) follow up protocol of care and compliance of preeclamptic women to protocol of care.

Through Mobile follow up protocol of care which entailed regular monitoring of (blood pressure, weight, edema degree, proteinuria and labs investigation, monitoring warning signs of PE, monitoring fetus condition for EFW, AFI and FMC) as well as health teaching about dietary control, controlling environmental noises and light, controlling exposure to smoking, maintain rest and activities through motab3a mobile application and instructional booklets. Women in the study group are frequently monitored for all mentioned variables, and abnormal finding detected by app women informed and referred to nearest health services.

The results of the current study revealed that, 90 of women in the study group comply with motab3a app, three quarter of women in the study group checked their blood pressure every 48 hrs, and input the results on Motab3a app, 86 % of women check their weight weekly according to protocol of follow up. Meanwhile 80% of women checked their proteinuria during antenatal visits, while 90% of women monitor their fetal movement daily, 70 % of women checked their labs investigation every antenatal visits, moreover 90% of women checked their fetus every two weeks through US according to protocol of follow up, 86 % of women attached their US reports to motab3a app.

The current study was in the same line with a cross-sectional study done by Mamat, & Sansuwito (2024) they design a user-friendly mobile application to support mothers with preeclampsia and their husbands in preventing eclampsia in Indonesia. The research was conducted in two phases: the first phase involved identifying the necessary content for eclampsia prevention, with 86 participants selected through convenience sampling. The second phase focused on developing the mobile application and conducting usability testing.

The results of the study concluded that the mobile application was easy to use, participants expressing confidence in its usability. All participants confirmed that the application contained the necessary and appropriate content for eclampsia prevention. The usability testing yielded positive feedback from both preeclamptic mothers and their husbands, highlighting the application's user-friendly design. The study also observed improvements in the knowledge and attitudes of users, promoting better self-care practices. Additionally, the application was noted for its time-saving benefits.

The current study in the same line with a case-control study conducted by Van den Heuvel et al (2020) to evaluated women with preeclampsia through use of a digital health platform for telemonitoring blood pressure and symptoms combined with preeclampsia. This care path integrates reduced in-person visits with a digital platform, **SAFE@HOME**, to ensure

continuous monitoring and support for pregnant individuals starting at 16 weeks of gestation. Through daily monitoring of blood pressure and symptoms, the platform aims to enhance prenatal care while maintaining safety and convenience. By enabling early detection of potential complications and fostering better communication between patients and healthcare providers.

Home measurements were monitored in-hospital by obstetric professionals, taking actions upon alarming results. This prospective SAFE@HOME group was compared to a retrospective control group managed without self-monitoring. The results of the study revealed that baseline characteristics of the SAFE@HOME (n = 103) and control group (n = 133) were comparable. In the SAFE@HOME group, antenatal visits (mean 13.7 vs 16.0, $p < 0.001$).

Section III; output approach of system theory entails the impact of mobile follow up protocol of care on the pregnancy outcomes.

The finding of the current study concerning pregnancy outcomes are maternal outcomes, fetal and neonatal outcomes.

In relation to maternal outcomes, the findings of the current study revealed that, a highly statistically significant difference between the study and control groups related to (mean of SBP, DPB, MAP, Degree of edema, proteinuria and maternal weigh gain), decrease rate of maternal complications during pregnancy, (14 %) of women in the study group as compared to (36 %) in control group experienced maternal complications during pregnancy e.g. (sever preeclampsia & APH). Low rate of hospital admission among the study group as compared to control group (22% & 38%) respectively, there highly statistically significance differences between the study and control groups regarding preterm delivery (4% & 26 %) respectively. 8.7% in the study group as compared to 32.7% in the control group had emergency Cs.

Concerning fetal outcomes, the results of the current study revealed that, there is statistical significance differences between both groups regarding fetal complication and lower rate of oligohydrominous among the study group as compared to control group (4%%& 16 %) respectively.

Regarding neonatal outcomes, findings of the current study revealed that there is statistical significance differences between both groups related to mean gestational age at time of delivery was 37.30 ± 0.81 weeks in the study group as compared to 35.50 ± 1.43 in the control group, and mean neonatal weight at time of delivery was 2933.60 ± 293.77 gm in the study group as compared to 2334.20 ± 342.10 gm of newborn in the control group and NICU stay as well as low rate of NICU admission among the study group as compared to control group.

Finding of the current study in the same line with a systematic review study carried out by Gholami et al (2022) to assess the effect of educations on the knowledge and pregnancy outcomes of pregnant women about HDP. They showed that educational program on pre-eclampsia increased the awareness of high-risk women significantly, which is reflected in

improving certain pregnancy outcomes like lower rate of NICU admission and mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure are lower in the study group as compared control group (The p-value of the mentioned outcomes was reported $p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the finding of the current study was in harmony with Van Den Heuvel et al (2020) to evaluate the use of a digital health platform for telemonitoring blood pressure and symptoms combined with a minimal antenatal visit schedule. The result of the study revealed admissions for hypertension or suspected preeclampsia were significantly fewer in the SAFE@HOME group (2.9% versus 13.5%, $p = 0.004$). Telemonitoring participants were highly satisfied using the platform. While, there is no statistical significance differences between both groups were observed for maternal and perinatal outcomes.

CONCLUSION

The current study concluded that mobile follow up protocol of care through motab3a mobile app had a significant effect improving maternal, fetal and neonatal outcomes

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are recommended:

1. Integrating the follow up protocol of care as a main part of antenatal care for women with mild preeclampsia
2. Raise awareness of women with preeclampsia that frequent monitoring and follow up allow early detection and management of the problem as well as safe her and baby life.
3. Raise the awareness of medical team staff about importance of integrating new technology in monitoring and educating women who at risk it may improve pregnancy outcomes
4. Future research to be replicated on larger sample size and different techniques for generalization of results.

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